

PERSEPHONE

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Abstract	The Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the life cycle of data within the PERSEPHONE Project, covering its production, collection, processing, storage, and preservation throughout the project's development and beyond.
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History of Changes

Version	Date	Reason of change
0.1 (draft)	24 Oct 2024	The initial draft of the document was distributed between PERSEPHONE project partners to review.
0.9	05 Dec 2024	DMP version for the final review with all the partners' inputs
1.0	11 Dec 2024	Final version of the document

Executive summary

The PERSEPHONE project aims to develop pioneering technologies for sustainable mining practices in support of the EU's Green Deal and the Critical Raw Materials Act. This document constitutes deliverable D10.5 for the Horizon Europe project PERSEPHONE. The Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the life cycle of data within the PERSEPHONE project, covering its production, collection, processing, storage, and preservation throughout the project's development and beyond. It details the processes for data collection, identifies the primary beneficiaries of the data, and describes the methods for data storage and management within the project.

The DMP also addresses the project's plans for making data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR principles). It specifies the resources required to ensure data openness and finalisation while taking into account security and ethical concerns in the project context. This document represents first version of the DMP, which is subject to updates and revisions as the project progresses to incorporate improvements. The plan also includes a report on the established data management facilities for the PERSEPHONE project.

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1. Abbreviations

CA	CONSORTIUM AGREEMENT
DMP	Data Management Plan
DLB	Deliverable Lead beneficiary
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable data
GA	Grant Agreement
PC	Project Coordinator
TP	Task partner

2. Introduction

2.1. Objectives of the PERSEPHONE Project

PERSEPHONE aims to develop new pioneering technologies for sustainable mining practices to assist the EU mining industry in reaching the goals of the Green Deal¹ and supporting the implementation of the Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA, 2024).

The project vision and concept include the:

- a. size reduction of the mining machine,
- b. the creation of a digital twin in support of autonomy for risk-aware navigation and full digitalisation of the extraction process,
- c. key enabling technologies at TRL5,
- d. novel approaches in online near-mine underground exploration core analysis,
- e. integration of data analytics for mine expansion.

PERSEPHONE aims to drive the green transition by minimising costs and waste in deep-mining operations, while also trying to achieve zero human presence in high-risk zones. This involves developing energy-efficient autonomous drilling machines with advanced perception capabilities for navigation, face drilling, and core extraction. These innovations will enable the creation of data-driven digital twins and geological models, enhancing decision support and optimising extraction planning.

2.2. Objectives of the deliverable

The purpose of the DMP is to ensure correct handling of the data with both respect to open access and exploitation of the results. The aim of this deliverable is to elaborate on and establish the data management procedures for all the mentioned types of data that will be created, gathered, processed, stored, and preserved throughout the lifetime of the PERSEPHONE project and ensure their applicability beyond the project's lifetime.

The following aspects of data management are to be covered in this report:

1. The **technical aspects** of managing the data generated or collected during the project
2. **Regulatory and ethical aspects** of data management including intellectual property rights (IPRs)
3. The **measures to ensure** that the data remain **FAIR** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable)

The project's efforts in the area of open research data are outlined giving particular attention to the following issues:

- The types of open and non-open data that will be generated or collected by the consortium, via experimental campaigns and research, during the project's lifespan;

¹ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/green-deal-industrial-plan/european-critical-raw-materials-act_en

- The technologies and infrastructures that will be used to securely preserve the data long-term;
- The standards used to encode the data;
- The data exploitation plans;
- The sharing/access policies applied to each data-set.

The DMP can be considered as a checklist for the future and as a reference for the resource and budget allocations related to data management. The content of this document builds upon the input of the project's beneficiaries throughout all the data related work-packages. A short email questionnaire, outlining the DMP's objectives and stating the required information in a structured manner, has been circulated by MineRP (MRP) and disseminated to the partners. The compiled answers have been integrated into a coherent plan as indicated in this document. The present DMP will evolve as the project progresses in accordance with the project's efforts in this area. At any time, the DMP will reflect the current state of the consortium's agreements regarding the data management, the exploitation and protection of rights and results.

The guiding principle of this plan shall be to show how the project implements Grant Agreement Annex 5, that concerns, limitations put by IPR, confidentiality, security and other business reasons, and in particular Article 17 concerns communication, dissemination, open science and visibility.

The content of the DMP follows the template provided by the EC². Further guidelines for working with a DMP is found in the Horizon Europe Programme Guide³.

2.2.1. Definitions

Some terms will be frequently found and are central to the DMP. Following are definitions of these terms:

- **Dataset** – “a collection of data that is treated as a single unit by a computer”.
- **Metadata** – “information that describes other information in order to help you understand or use it”. In this context it is a file that contains information about the dataset such that it can be quickly found and easily understood.

2.3. Report Structure

The document follows the established Horizon Europe template for a Data Management Plan (DMP).

² This DMP follows the template “Data management plan (HE):V1.1 – _01.04.2022” _obtained from the Funding & Tenders Portal [Reference Documents page](#) > Templates & form

³ [HE Programme Guide](#) is found in the Funding & Tenders Portal [Reference Documents page](#) > Guidance. Latest version at the time of writing is V4.0 (15 October 2023)

3. Data Summary

This chapter provides definitions and working procedures for the data management.

3.1. Work Packages and Expected Data

This section provides a more contextual explanation of the data generated within the project. The various datatypes are also further explained in section 3.2. All work packages have associated **Deliverables**, and the reports classified as 'public' are made available through the project website.

WP 1: - Specification and requirements for enabling sustainable deep mining

This WP is focused on getting a deeper understanding of the definitions, specifications and the conceptualisation of operation and development in adopting smart, sustainable and autonomous deep-mining exploration and extraction practices. **Research and requirements data** are gathered and compiled in the corresponding **Deliverables**.

WP 2 & 3: -Technologies for Smart, Sustainable and Energy efficient Deposit Exploration and Extraction Systems

In these WPs novel technologies for a) mineral exploration, b) adaptive production drilling, c) real time rock mass characterisation systems are being developed for underground mines. **Design drawings** of the mineral exploration drilling systems will be developed. Sensor data from the **drill hole monitoring** systems, **real time rock characterisation** will be gathered. Calibrations and initial tests of sensors as well as analyses of the rock mass preconditioning and exploration drilling processing performance will yield various forms of **experimental data**.

WP 4 & 5: - Intelligence for Independent and Autonomous Deep Mine Drilling Exploration and Extraction System

These WPs are dedicated to the development of the autonomy stack (modular components that can be integrated into customers' robotic systems) required for autonomous deep mining exploration/production drilling and excavation machines. This will yield further large amounts of **simulation** and **experimental data** ranging from raw sensor data to processed data and final outputs in form of demonstration videos. The algorithm development for the autonomous guidance, navigation and control of the mining and drilling robots will also yield **code**.

WP 6: - Technologies for On-line Analytics Capabilities for Face Drilling and Extraction

This WP deals with equipping the mining machines with sensing and analytics capacities to enable autonomous near-mine exploration. **Design** of the sensor system for both invasive and non-invasive assessment of the ore body are being developed. Calibrations and initial tests of sensors as well as analyses of the ore processing performance will yield various forms of **experimental data**.

WP7 - Data-driven and dynamic Geo-modelling Synthesis for efficient extraction Developments

In this WP, digitisation of mines is aimed for with the help of digital twins that will help estimate the outcomes of future drilling, assist in long-term ore-extraction planning, and enable safe extraction in deep mining operations. This will generate the **predictive analytics data, logistics and supply chain data, sustainability and compliance data**, which will further lead to **mining protocols** processes.

WP 8 & 9 Integration and Concept Evaluation

The work packages are dedicated to the integration of various technologies in different WPs together and evaluating the proposed methods. Various forms of **experimental data** will be obtained, including **scientific data** (measurements by the sensors) as well as **demonstration videos**.

WP 10 & 11 Outreach and Exploitation

Besides the actual material that is presented – **text data** in form of journal papers, newsletters, presentations, social media posts – the dissemination and communication activities will mostly result in reports of planned and performed activities.

WP 12 & 13 Management & Coordination

These are the administrative work packages. They involve managing legal, ethical and financial issues, reporting to the EC and ensuring communication between all project partners and tasks. The relevant data include financial data and project progress reports. Except for some Deliverables, the majority of data will be confidential.

Table 1: Summary of datasets that will be utilized for the PERSEPHONE project

Type	Data	Possible Format	Requires spatial coordinates	UNFC Requirement	Digital Twin Development	Description
Geological Database	Drill hole data	Table	Yes	Yes	Yes	Records from drilling operations detailing subsurface geology
	Sample data	Table	Yes	Yes	Yes	Analyses of physical samples taken from surface or rock face
	Lithology/Rock Type	Table	Yes	Yes	Yes	Classification of rocks based on their physical and chemical composition
	Alteration	Table	Yes	Yes	Yes	Classification of the alteration in the rocks
	Mineralogy	Table	Yes	Yes	Yes	Study of minerals within the geological samples
	Assay (Composition)	Table	Yes	Essential	Yes	Chemical composition of selected target elements
	Structure	Table	Yes	Yes	Yes	Geological features such as faults and folds
	Geotechnical/rockmass	Table	Yes	Yes	Yes	Mechanical properties and behaviour of the rock mass
Geological model	Lithology	Surface/Wireframe	Integrated	Yes	Essential	3D representation of different rock types
	Alteration	Surface/Wireframe	Integrated	Yes	Yes	3D representation of different alteration types
	Structure	Surface/Wireframe	Integrated	Yes	Essential	3D visualization of geological structures
	Grade	Surface/Wireframe	Integrated	Essential	Essential	Distribution of ore grade within the rock mass
	Geotechnical	Surface/Wireframe	Integrated	Yes	Yes	3D model of geotechnical properties

Resource model	Grade/Ore body	Shells/Block	Integrated	Essential	Essential	3D volumes representing the concentration and distribution of ore
	Estimation parameters	Table	Integrated	Essential	Yes	Data used to estimate the quantity and quality of the resource
Geophysical Data	Seismic/magnetic/IP data	3D visualizations/Maps	Yes	Yes	Yes	Subsurface imaging data to identify geological formations
	Downhole data	Table/sections	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Infrastructure	Topography (LIDAR)	3D models/Point clouds	Yes	No (for deep UG mine)	No (for deep UG mine)	topographic data for detailed surface mapping
	Mine workings	3D/Map	Yes	Yes	Essential	Layout and design of the mine's physical structure
Environmental and Social Data	Environmental Impact Assessments	Reports/Maps	For monitoring	Essential	Essential	Studies on the potential environmental impacts of mining operations
	Social Impact Assessments	Reports/Maps	For monitoring	Essential	Essential	Studies on the potential social impacts, including community engagement
	Hydrological Data	Maps/Models	Yes	Yes	Yes	Data on water flow and distribution within the mine area
	Environmental Monitoring	Sensors/Database	Yes	Essential	Essential	Real-time data on environmental conditions impacting mining operations
Mine Planning	Mine schedule	Gantt Charts/Tables		Yes	Essential	Detailed plan for mining operations over time
	Future works	Project management tools		Yes	Essential	Projections for future expansions and development activities
	Logistics Data	Supply Chain Management System		Yes	Yes	Information on the transportation and logistics of materials and resources

Geo-metallurgical Data	Metallurgical characteristics	Table/Graphs/Models		Essential	Yes	Information on the variability in metallurgical response of the ore across the deposit
	Recovery rates	Table/Graphs		Essential	Yes	Expected recovery percentages based on processing methods
	Liberation characteristics	Table/Graphs/Models		Yes	Yes	The degree to which minerals are freed from the gangue minerals
	Comminution parameters	Table/Graphs		Yes	Yes	Data describing how the ore breaks down in crushers and mills
Mine Operational Data	Production data	Table/Real-time stream		Essential	Essential	Data related to the quantity and rate of ore extraction
	Ore flow diagrams	Diagrams/Models		Essential	Yes	Detailed diagrams showing the flow of material through the various stages of mining
	Equipment performance	Table/Logs		Yes	Yes	Records and analyses of mining equipment efficiency and maintenance
	Storage	Database/Inventory system		Yes	Yes	Information on the storage capacity and inventory management
Processing Data	Process flow diagrams	Diagrams/Models		Essential	Yes	Detailed diagrams showing the flow of material through the various stages of the processing plant
	Tailings characteristics	Table/Reports		Essential	Yes	Characteristics of tailings, including potential recoveries and environmental considerations

3.2. Purpose of data collection/generation

The purpose of data collection/generation in the PERSEPHONE project is to develop new realistic simulation models representing deep or abandoned underground mines. The data collected/ generated will contain and share the open data that are going to be produced from various technical activities of the project and that could be reused by other researchers in the field (while respecting the PERSEPHONE data sharing policy). The data will be actively used for research, as an input for analysis, and included in documentation and publications. The types of collected/generated data in this project can be roughly categorised into four categories:

- Simulation data
- Measurements gathered in experimental lab facilities or in field trials
- Personal data
- Documentation

Simulation data will be generated by all project partners in the project throughout their research, development and innovation work in the corresponding WPs. This will consist of mathematical models of sensors, mining machines, unmanned aerial vehicles and other related sources.

Various measurements from different environmental sensors and onboard sensors on mining machines and robots operating in mining environments will be collected throughout the duration of the project. These data will be used to verify the mathematical models and research and development assumptions in performing the planned activities of PERSEPHONE. The project will also collect and process data to map the environment (point clouds, odometry) and provide the user with information for remote operation.

During experiments, some personal data of people might be gathered, for example if they appear in videos or when giving personal feedback during the tests. For such cases a consent form for signing is provided (see Appendix 1). It is yet unclear how much and what types of data will be gathered, so the DMP will be updated throughout the duration of the project. Personal data of people signing up for project events might be collected to facilitate and validate registration. Only the organising institution will have access to this data. A small amount of personal data might be also gathered from users of the PERSEPHONE website when sending an enquiry about the project. The purpose of gathering these data is only to better address the individual inquiries. Such data will always follow the GDPR guidelines (see the section 4.7).

Documentation written as part of this project is considered generated data. This includes internal project documents that provide guidelines for everyday activities, deliverables, and reports for the European Commission.

3.3. Types of Data

Various types of data will be generated throughout the PERSEPHONE project. The majority of this will include sensor data and analyses of collected samples, particularly during the integration and concept evaluation phases. The key data types identified as relevant for the PERSEPHONE project are listed in Table 1.

The primary purpose of categorising the data into types is to offer a clearer structure for their management. Experimental data are further divided into subcategories, as shown in Table 2, allowing for a more organised approach to directly managing data produced by the project's experiments.

Both qualitative and quantitative data will be collected during the course of the project. All project data will be stored in digital form. To the greatest extent possible, the data gathered and generated will be formatted in standard, system-independent formats.

Table 1: Data types

ID	Category	Description
DES	Design	<i>Drawings and technical requirements</i>
EXP*	Experimental data	Output from, or input to, tests (pilot trials or preparatory investigations) - process parameters - sensors output, raw data or (pre-) processed data - output from analysis
S/W	Software	Generated software, algorithm or code in MATLAB, Robot Operating System (ROS), Python and C++, software documentation (Wiki, GitLab, GitHub)
TEXT	Text and reports	Structured/unstructured data in form of text in the form of reports and other (PDF, XLS, PPTX, DOCX, TeX)
OBS#	Observational	Observation from an experiment or mining processes. It may contain images (PNG, JPEG, RAW, TIFF, BMP), and Videos (MP4, AVI, MKV)

* Sub-categories to EXP are specified in Table 3

Table 3: Subcategories to the EXP category

Sub-ID	Subcategory	Description
MP	Mine plan data	- In-time/parametric planning data - Mining cycle data Feedback data (impact on production profile) - Re-scheduling data (impact on enterprise resource planning)
SENS	Sensor data	- Raw navigation sensor data: Images (PNG, JPEG, RAW, TIFF, BMP), Videos (MP4, AVI,

		MKV), LiDAR pointcloud, RGB-D, ROS bags, CSV, TXT. - Mineral sensor data from a single sensor. For example: chemical composition, volume, ore classification, etc. Measure While Drilling (MWD) data – physical machine measurements, .XLM Hole Probing data – probing to determine the actual drill hole position, .DXF
SIM	Simulation data	Output from the MATLAB/Python, Gazebo, Unity simulations.
PRO	Processed Data	Final output obtained from analysis algorithms of combined sensor data.

3.4. Data Conversions

3.4.1. Formats for specific data types

File format and compatibility are essential for ensuring accessibility and fluidity on exchanging documents between different partners using different systems. It also foresees the preservation of data, to ensure that it can be archived and retrieved in the future.

Standardisation here ensures that documents can be easily shared, reused and preserved over time. The following file formats shall be used:

- Word processor documents – Microsoft Office WORD version 2003 or higher (.doc or .docx formats);
- Spreadsheet documents – Microsoft Office EXCEL version 2003 or higher (.xls or .xlsx formats);
- Presentations – Microsoft Office POWERPOINT version 2003 or higher (.ppt or .pptx formats);
- Promotional materials (flyers, newsletters) or other non-editable project documents– PDF format;
- For compressed files – ZIP format.
- Bitmap image files – JPEG or PNG formats
- Vector graphics files – EMF, DXF or SVG formats
- Video files - MP4 (H.264 + ACC).

Adhering to these standardised file formats will ensure that documents can be easily shared and read by all Consortium partners, regardless of their operating system or software preferences. Moreover, using these formats will facilitate the preservation of the documents, enabling their retrieval and use in the future.

3.4.2. Document Naming and Coding

To ensure efficient management and easy retrieval of data over time, it is crucial to use a structured file naming convention and maintain consistency in the document reference structure. This approach will create a unique identifier for all PERSEPHONE documents stored on SharePoint. The prescribed naming convention is:

- PERSEPHONE_[DOCUMENT CODE]_[DOCUMENT NAME]_v[VERSION NUMBER]_[CONTRIBUTOR INITIALS]

Examples of this structure are given below for different document types:

- Deliverables shall be named: PERSEPHONE_...;
- Meeting Minutes shall be named: PERSEPHONE_ Meeting minutes_ 20231210_v1.0 ...

The version numbering system should be unique and easy to track. The initial draft of the document shall be version 0.1. Subsequent draft versions shall be numbered 0.2, 0.3, and so on. Once the document is finalised and published, it should be assigned version 1.0. If minor changes are made to the published document, the version should be updated to 1.1, 1.2, and so on. For significant changes, the version shall be updated to 2.0. For more detailed information on PERSEPHONE's document naming and coding, please refer to Deliverable 10.5 Project Management Plan.

3.5. Data accessibility and access rights

The strive is to make relevant data accessible to the interested public such that results can be verified and lessons learned can be shared. However, not all data can be shared publicly. For example, when they contain sensitive information on mining processes, reveal properties of products which are or are intended to be commercialised, or if they touch in some other way the intellectual property rights (IPRs) of project partners or other collaborators. For personal data, GDPR guidelines will be strictly followed (see the section 4.7). Data that can be made available to the public will be labelled PU and sensitive (confidential) data will be labelled SEN, as listed in Table4.

Table 4: Accessibility

ID	Types	Description
PU	Public	Public data
SEN	Sensitive	Confidential data

3.6. Reusing Existing data

Some external data might be reused in the project, for example to assess the state-of-the-art or to use pre-existing models of similar systems. This is expected to be publicly available data and not be restricted by any use licenses.

Furthermore, some of the beneficiaries will reuse some of their own pre-existing data. This is stated in more detail in Attachment 1 of the PERSEPHONE Consortium Agreement and if not agreed otherwise these data are considered as background IPR (BIPR).

3.7. Data origin

As mentioned before, part of the data (such as simulations and software) will be generated directly by the participants of the project in almost all the WPs. Measurements will also be collected from laboratory or field experiments, trials, and demonstrations. Proper care will be taken to gather the necessary

measurements while complying with GDPR and individual regulations of the facility owners.

3.8. Expected volume of data

The expected total volume size of the generated and collected data is on the order of Terabytes, with the largest portion consisting of measurement-derived data. Videos and images will be by far the most numerous and voluminous types of data.

A rough size estimate of total project data is around 5-10 TB, but this depends very much on the type of experiments and the planned times for field trials and demonstrations that are going to be performed, as well as on the data formats that are going to be utilized.

3.9. Data utility (to whom will it be useful)

First and foremost, the data will be used by the PERSEPHONE participants for reaching the project goals, as well as in future research and demonstration directions. Project results produced datasets that are going to be opened publicly for both the academic and industrial sectors that have an interest in these mining areas.

4. Management of Sensitive Data

To ensure that PERSEPHONE upholds its commitment to protect the confidentiality and privacy of its contributors, it is crucial to exercise the utmost discretion when handling sensitive data. This involves adhering to applicable legal requirements described in GA, Annex 5 and implementing appropriate measures to safeguard against unauthorised access, theft, or data loss.

4.1. Identification of Sensitive Data

Sensitive data are data that are either private or confidential. The first refers primarily to personal data, and the second refers to data that may also be derived from secondary data shall not be disseminated.

4.2. Access to Sensitive Data

It is essential to collect the minimum amount of personal information possible. Such information shall comprise on only those data that are essential to communicate with the project participants and other contributors. Sensitive information must only be accessible to designated members of the project coordination team and must not be disclosed.

For restricted datasets, access will be managed by the beneficiary responsible for the data generation or the corresponding host institution. If possible, these datasets will be curated, so that they can be shared with as many as possible, without compromising confidential or IPR protected information.

4.3. Informed Consent

To ensure ethical data collection processes and the protection of individuals' rights, the informed consent of contributors or participants in public events must be obtained a priori. Furthermore, it is mandatory to ensure that the data collected are only used for the stated purposes and they must not be used for any other purposes without the explicit consent of the respective persons. This ensures that confidentiality and their privacy are respected and protected throughout the project.

4.4. Storage of sensitive data

Personal data gathered by the consortium and internal project documents will be stored on a SharePoint site created through Microsoft Teams, where only consortium members have access.

4.5. Sharing of Data Among the Consortium

If it is necessary to share raw data with entitled Consortium members, they shall not be sent by emails, but through a dedicated private channel on the MS Teams platform. MS Teams data transfers are encrypted to ensure privacy of data in transit. Finally, all personal data will be deleted from the MS Teams channel at the end of the project. A log shall be kept by all data holders of such transfers, recording which data-files when and to whom had been transferred.

4.6. Holding Times of Sensitive Data

Sensitive data states must be securely stored and then destroyed no later than 60 days after the project's completion. This protocol serves a dual purpose. Firstly, it enables Consortium partners to access the data if there is any uncertainty

regarding the validity of conclusions drawn from it. Secondly, it ensures that sensitive data are not retained for an extended period, thereby minimising the potential risk of unauthorised access or misuse.

During project lifespan and for four years afterward, the beneficiaries must keep confidential any data, documents or other material (in any form) that is identified as confidential at the time it is disclosed ('confidential information').

If a beneficiary requests, the European Commission may agree to keep such information confidential for an additional period beyond the initial four years.

If information has been identified as confidential only orally, it will be considered to be confidential only if this is confirmed in writing within 15 days of the oral disclosure.

4.7. Accessibility of Sensitive Data by Persons Concerned

As per the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR; European Parliament and Council, 2016), individuals have the right to request access to their data that is being held. To ensure compliance, the consent form template includes provisions that prohibit the publication of any data without the contributor's written authorisation. However, if any concerns arise at a later stage, they can be addressed to the contact person mentioned in the consent form, who is responsible for the activity. Alternatively, concerns can be directed to the Project Coordinator. Upon receiving such concerns, the Project Coordinator shall respond within 10 days and make the necessary changes within a further 10 days. This process ensures that data is handled responsibly and transparently while safeguarding individuals' rights.

5. FAIR data

5.1. Making data accessible according to the FAIR principle

Data in general will be shared at different access levels according to the principle “as open as possible, as restricted as necessary”, for instance by publishing metadata only.

The European Commission demands that data generated by projects they fund remain FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, see Wilkinson et al., 2016).

To facilitate data discoverability, metadata will be associated to all data files archived in an open research repository during the PERSEPHONE project. Because of the diversity of data types, several metadata formats might be used. We will strive to use standard metadata formats. All published data will have a DOI associated, making it citable and findable. DOI for datasets will be provided in the related scientific publications. The metadata of the datasets will follow a standard format, the DataCite metadata schema.

All datasets, software libraries and code uploaded on the shared research data repository will be automatically assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) via DataCite. This makes them citable in the same way as articles in scientific journals and makes the data easily identifiable.

Common naming conventions for the data files will be utilised. The names need to be self-explanatory and unique, while being as short as possible. The following information should be contained in the name:

- Project acronym
- Date when file was generated
- Identifier of data type
- Beneficiary/Partner identification number
- Author/source person’s initials
- Short description of data file

The exact naming convention will be settled later in the project, after consortium has a more comprehensive view on the types of data files used.

The metadata generated for each published dataset, software library, code or publication will include keywords. Some of these keywords will be consistently associated with the project and repeated in the social media channels. In this way, it will be easier to discover the data related to PERSEPHONE.

The platform that will be used for publishing the research data will follow Commission’s recommendations and support version control. So, each new file version automatically receives a unique DOI. The old versions of the file will still be accessible and still have the originally assigned DOI. Data platforms will be introduced in subsection 5.2.

5.2. Making data openly accessible

As stated in the PERSEPHONE Grant Agreement, Annex 5, beneficiaries must ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications related to their results, the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publications, and the research data needed to validate the presented results. Furthermore, information about software, tools and instruments necessary for validating the results must be included and, if possible, the software, tools and instruments themselves.

The PERSEPHONE consortium will share all these data to the greatest extent possible. Some exceptions might arise for datasets collected on-site, at industrial facilities of partners that might have legitimate interest not to disclose the collected data. As such exceptions are not known yet, agreements with individual partners on each dataset will be concluded on the information that can be made publicly available.

European law mandates that code generated by its employees is owned by the employer. All software/code needs legal evaluation (commercialisation, copyright and use license) before sharing outside the institution or before publication.

Training material, such as presentations and lectures, will be made available on the project website (either directly or through a link to a public repository). Personal data and internal project documents will not be made public due to obvious reasons.

All research results, public data and associated metadata, documentation, and code will be published on Zenodo, an open-access research data repository operated by CERN. There, data are made freely accessible in accordance with Open Science ideals and the FAIR principles. Whenever possible, the data will be converted into formats that can be opened using public domain software. If specific tools will be required to access some datasets, this will be indicated in the respective metadata file. Related code, software libraries or documentation generated by consortium members to access or visualise the data will be added to the research data repository as well (unless they are protected by IPR confidentiality or are commercial-in-confidence, cf. Ch. 4).

All public data and associated metadata, documentation and code will be published on a research data repository, Zenodo. For user convenience, code and associated data might also be deposited on individual or laboratory servers or Git repositories. The research data or code that cannot be made public (due to IPR, confidentiality requests by partners, that needs to be curated before being made public, or is still under peer review) will be stored on individual beneficiaries' repositories. Personal data gathered by the consortium and internal project documents will be stored on a SharePoint site created through Microsoft Teams, where only consortium members have access.

For restricted datasets, access will be managed by the beneficiary responsible for the data generation or the corresponding host institution. If possible, these

datasets will be curated, so that they can be shared with as many as possible, without compromising confidential or IPR protected information. Data in general could be shared on different access levels according to the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”, for instance by publishing metadata only.

5.3. Making data interoperable

To make data interoperable, we will use widely accepted, open standards and data formats, as well as standard vocabulary for all data types whenever possible. The metadata will contain information on the software used for generating the data and, in case of developed software, this will be published as well, where it is allowed from the IPR agreement. The published research data on the Zenodo repository will follow the DataCite metadata scheme. For all datasets and software, we will include information on the use licenses. Where possible, geolocated data will follow INSPIRE directive guidelines.

5.4. Increase data re-use

We will use the Creative Common CCBY 4.0 license recommended by the European Commission for research data. For software, appropriate open licenses will be chosen after legal evaluation and advice. Data associated with publications will not be open during the peer review process. In some cases, this could lead to embargos of more than two years after the finalization of the project. After a publication is approved, the data associated with it will be published no later than at the time of publication, under the conditions stated in the grant agreement and consortium agreement. Most of the data generated as part of the project will likely be available for reuse without any restrictions. Each beneficiary will be responsible for assuring data quality for their own generated/collected datasets. The consortium will periodically check that existing data follows a minimum quality standard. Finally, the data stored on the open research server will be available for re-use several years after the project ends. The exact period will be decided later, after assessing the data impact and long-term storage costs.

5.1. Data security

Public project data will be published on Zenodo. The data is stored on servers managed according to the CERN Security Baseline for Servers and which always have the latest security patches applied. Each data file is stored on two different disk servers, and it can be fully recovered in case of file corruption. Beneficiaries will use their own institutional servers to store data that cannot be made public or that has not yet been curated or published. In this case, each beneficiary is responsible for securely storing, accessing, and backing up the data. Project documents and personal data are stored on the Microsoft Teams platform, which uses the ISO27001 standard. Transferring of personal data outside of this shared platform is not expected but, if it will be necessary, encrypted file-sharing tools and methods will be used.

6. Allocation of resources

The Zenodo research data repository can be used free of charge. In terms of software, we will strive to use open access or software widely used both in academia and industry, so that no associated costs are needed to make it FAIR. Costs for gold open access publishing of scientific articles will be covered by individual beneficiary project budget. Hybrid open access is not recommended, as it might not be eligible for reimbursement. In the context of this project, the Project Manager will be responsible for making sure that the DMP is followed and will provide guidance to project participants concerning data management. The Project Manager will also update the DMP any time conditions change. Each beneficiary of the PERSEPHONE will have the responsibility to ensure that the data they generate or collect is FAIR. They will upload the data to the shared research repository, providing metadata, keywords, etc.

7. Data security

As it has been mentioned, the public project data will be published on Zenodo. The data is stored on servers managed according to the CERN Security Baseline for Servers and which always have the latest security patches applied. Each data file is stored on two different disk servers, and it can be fully recovered in case of file corruption. Beneficiaries will use their own institutional servers to store data that cannot be made public or that has not yet been curated or published. In this case, each beneficiary is responsible for securely storing, accessing, and backing up the data. Project documents and personal data are stored on the Microsoft Teams platform, which uses the ISO27001 standard. Transferring of personal data outside of this shared platform is not expected but, if it will be necessary, encrypted file-sharing tools and methods will be used.

8. Ethical aspects

To the best of understanding of the PERSEPHONE project partners, there are no ethical or legal issues with the generated data that could have an impact on the data sharing. Each partner will conduct research and development actions following The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA, 2023) and the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (European Parliament, 2000), such as the need to ensure the freedom of research and the need to protect the physical and moral integrity of individuals and the welfare of animals.

This DMP also contains a consent form (Appendix 1) to be used for instance when meetings, site visits etc. are recorded to ask individual participants their permission to use such recordings in public.

9. Conclusions

To ensure compliance with the European legislative framework concerning data management, this Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines guidelines for managing data generated or collected in the context of PERSEPHONE.

The DMP asserts that the PERSEPHONE Consortium fully complies with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in all its internal conduct documents, such as the Grant and Consortium Agreements. Additionally, recognising and respecting Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) when collecting secondary data is crucial to acknowledge the work of others properly.

Another section of the DMP differentiates between the different types of data to be collected and sets standards for their management. This includes guidelines for data handling, such as document storage, accepted file formats, and establishing a document naming and coding system.

Furthermore, rules for data sharing are defined in this section. Sensitive data shall be kept confidential to protect the privacy and security of the providers. The main ethical and privacy issues related to sensitive data involve ensuring that data remain private and that proper consent is obtained before collecting, processing, sharing or publishing it.

For data and deliverables with a 'public' dissemination level, the primary challenge is to ensure that it is communicated using practices that make them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR), while respecting Intellectual Property Rights (IPR).

To guarantee the appropriate dissemination of public deliverables, specific provisions are outlined in the Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation (D10.4).

Effective data management is central to PERSEPHONE's success, and adherence by partners to the guidelines laid out in this document is critical in all phases of the project.

10. References

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Appendix 1 – Template for PERSEPHONE event participant information sheet

This document must be adapted to specific aspects of the project activities (e.g. site visits, demonstration videos, etc.). The information may be provided in bullet points or in a question-answer format, mentioning the items below. If deemed necessary, the information may be supplied in another language than English, but with the English version appended for reference.

The purpose of the information sheet and the associated consent form is that the rights of persons appearing in pictures and video and persons being interviewed are aware of their rights under the GDPR and have given their necessary consent.

- 1) Title of Work Package;
- 2) Name of the activity;
- 3) Short description of PERSEPHONE and the overall aim of the activity;
- 4) The place (if applicable), and the expected duration of the activity;
- 5) Describe, how the material will be used (reports, publications, presentations, videos, social media posts);
- 6) Name and contact of the responsible for the activity;
- 7) Statement of confidentiality;
- 8) Information that participation is totally voluntary and the participants are free to withdraw;
- 9) Procedure for contacting the project with any concerns or complaints.

Template for consent form

PERSEPHONE PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

Title of Work Package _____

Name of the activity _____

		YES	NO
1.	I have read the Information Sheet for this activity and have had details of the work explained to me.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.	My questions about PERSEPHONE's planned use of the material have been answered to my satisfaction and I understand that I may ask further questions at any point.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.	I understand that I am free to withdraw from this activity at any time without giving a reason for my withdrawal or to decline to answer any particular question without any consequences to my future treatment by the researchers.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.	I wish to participate in this PERSEPHONE activity under the conditions set out in the Information Sheet.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Name _____

Signature _____

Date _____

Contact details (email; phone) _____

PERSEPHONE contact person's name _____

PERSEPHONE contact person's contact details (email; phone)

PERSEPHONE contact person's signature _____

Please keep your copy of the consent form and the information sheet together.